

Narrative review

A Mechanism-Based Strategy to Prevent NSAID-Induced Gastrointestinal Injury: Step-down Switching to Acetaminophen Based on 1-Week Evaluation of NSAID Efficacy

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Conflict of Interest:

The author reports that his child is employed by Nippon Zoki Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd., a company that manufactures and markets analgesic products, including tramadol, acetaminophen, tramadol/acetaminophen combination tablets, and Neurotropin®, which may represent a conflict of interest.

Abstract:

Conventional strategies for preventing nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID)-induced gastrointestinal (GI) injury have primarily focused on gastroprotective agents, particularly proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). However, PPIs do not fully prevent NSAID-induced GI injury and are associated with an increased risk of lower GI injury and various PPI-related adverse events. This review discusses clinical strategies to minimize NSAID exposure. Based on limited evidence, the following strategies are suggested:

1. Because the efficacy of NSAIDs for neuropathic or nociplastic pain (NNP) is limited, NSAIDs may be avoided in patients with predominantly NNP.
2. Prioritize topical NSAIDs or acetaminophen for mild pain.
3. Analgesic efficacy may be evaluated approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation. However, this evaluation may be delayed by up to 2 weeks. Patients referred from other institutions may be managed using the same evaluation time frame.
4. If pain is reduced at the time of evaluation, NSAIDs may be discontinued or switched to acetaminophen to reduce NSAID exposure, or once adequate pain relief is achieved, without waiting for 1 week.

5. If pain is not reduced at the time of evaluation, reevaluate the pain mechanism and consider modifying management: NNP-targeted agents may be considered if NNP predominates, or opioids or more potent NSAIDs if NcP predominates.

In addition, adjunctive strategies—including topical NSAIDs, non-pharmacologic interventions, and *Helicobacter pylori* eradication therapy—may further contribute to reducing overall NSAID exposure. However, COX-2-selective NSAIDs do not sufficiently mitigate risks.

These strategies were implemented in clinical practice, markedly reducing overall NSAID use without any reported cases of severe NSAID-induced GI injury in the author's clinical experience. By focusing on the reduction of unnecessary NSAID exposure, this approach may serve as a practical strategy to prevent NSAID-induced GI injury and may additionally mitigate other NSAID-related adverse events, including renal impairment and cardiovascular events.

Key Words:

nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID)-induced gastrointestinal injury, acetaminophen, proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), early evaluation, early discontinuation, nociceptive pain, topical NSAIDs, eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*

1 Introduction

Gastroprotective agents such as proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are widely used to prevent nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID)-induced gastrointestinal (GI) injury. Indeed, PPIs reduce the risk of NSAID-induced ulcers ⁽¹⁾. However, PPIs do not fully prevent NSAID-induced GI injury ⁽¹⁾. Moreover, PPIs have been reported to increase the risk of NSAID-induced small intestinal injury ⁽²⁾, and various PPI-associated adverse events have also been reported in recent years ⁽³⁾. Traditionally, preventive strategies for NSAID-induced GI injury have focused primarily on concomitant gastroprotective agents. Although reduction of NSAID exposure is generally recommended in clinical practice, specific clinical methods for achieving this are not yet well established. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence guideline on osteoarthritis in over 16s: diagnosis and management recommends that, if pharmacological treatments are required, they should be used at the lowest effective dose for the shortest possible time ⁽⁴⁾, a principle also applicable to NSAID therapy. However, such general recommendations alone may be insufficient to meaningfully change prescribing practices. Therefore, as a pragmatic approach, a 1-week evaluation of NSAID efficacy followed by switching to acetaminophen is proposed. Although direct evidence supporting a specific time frame is limited, specifying a concrete time point may help reduce unnecessarily prolonged use of NSAIDs.

Clinical strategies to reduce NSAID exposure are reviewed, including analgesic selection based on pain mechanisms, early evaluation of NSAID efficacy, and switching to acetaminophen as an alternative. While this review addresses areas with limited evidence, it proposes a framework that integrates pathophysiological mechanisms with

clinical decision-making to guide clinical practice. This narrative review provides a hypothesis-generating framework to inform clinical practice rather than a definitive guideline.

2 Methods

This narrative review was based on literature identified in PubMed from 2003 to the present. Full-text reviews were conducted for the primary articles, and related literature was collated. Additional searches were conducted for each topic to supplement the available evidence. The final literature search covered articles indexed in PubMed up to April 24, 2026. This framework was developed by integrating evidence-based insights into clinical practice to bridge the gap between existing evidence and practice.

3 Pain Mechanisms and NSAID Responsiveness

From an etiological perspective, the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) classifies pain into three categories: nociceptive pain (NcP), neuropathic pain (NeP), and nociplastic pain (NpP) ⁽⁵⁾. Pharmacological treatments recommended for NeP and NpP share many similarities ⁽⁶⁾, and both conditions are poorly responsive to NSAIDs ^(7,8). Therefore, it is not always necessary to strictly distinguish between these conditions when considering strategies to reduce NSAID exposure. For practical purposes, this review treats both conditions collectively as “neuropathic or nociplastic pain (NNP)” based on their shared clinical feature of poor responsiveness to NSAIDs. This approach allows relatively straightforward clinical decision-making even for non-specialist physicians. Differentiation between NcP and NNP, as well as the evaluation of their co-occurrence, should be based on a thorough clinical evaluation, which includes the extent, characteristics, duration, and cause of pain, along with a physical examination. Detailed diagnostic methods for these distinctions are beyond the scope of this review and are not addressed here. As the focus of this review is on the reduction of NSAID exposure, specific pharmacological treatments for NNP are described in previously published guidelines ^(7,9). Persistent pain may increase the contribution of NNP, resulting in a relative decrease in the proportion of pure NcP over time ⁽¹⁰⁾.

NSAIDs are generally considered effective analgesics for NcP, whereas their efficacy for NNP is limited. Therefore, when NNP is considered the predominant pain mechanism and NcP contributes minimally, it may be reasonable to avoid NSAIDs as an initial treatment and instead select agents effective for NNP. Diabetic peripheral neuropathy is a typical form of NeP. However, patients with this condition may also have predominantly NcP, such as pain associated with knee osteoarthritis. In such individual cases, NSAIDs may represent an appropriate therapeutic option.

Following this strategy may facilitate a seamless transition from treatments targeting NcP to those targeting NNP. Moreover, as discussed below, the effectiveness of analgesics for NcP can generally be evaluated in the short term, whereas that for NNP cannot be readily evaluated in the short term. Therefore, when mixed pain involving

both NcP and NNP is suspected, or when the pain mechanism is unclear, it may be reasonable to initiate treatment for NcP first.

In this context, an early response to NSAIDs may serve not only as an evaluation of therapeutic efficacy but also as a diagnostic test to help infer the underlying pain mechanism.

4 Principles of Pharmacological Management

(1) General Recommendation

In general, if adequate pain relief is not achieved and adverse events do not limit dose escalation, analgesics for NNP should be titrated to the maximum recommended dose, as recommended for NeP based on the available evidence ⁽⁹⁾. A similar approach may be applied to NcP. However, for NSAIDs, the initial dose is often the maximum recommended dose. If adequate pain relief is not achieved at the maximum recommended dose, a dose reduction or discontinuation should be considered, and switching to an alternative agent may be considered ⁽⁹⁾. Prolonged use of analgesics with unclear efficacy is undesirable. In addition, NSAIDs are contraindicated in patients with severe renal impairment.

For mild pain, acetaminophen or topical NSAIDs may be used in place of oral NSAIDs as an initial treatment, as these are generally reasonable options.

After NSAID initiation, it is desirable to evaluate analgesic efficacy and document the findings in the medical record. In general, continuing medications without evaluation of efficacy is undesirable.

(2) Personal Recommendation

For mild pain, patients may be advised to use acetaminophen or topical NSAIDs in place of oral NSAIDs as an initial treatment, as these are generally reasonable options.

A considerable number of patients may request NSAIDs even for mild pain. In such cases, patients may be advised to use both NSAIDs and acetaminophen and compare their post-treatment pain levels, where feasible. If no difference in post-treatment pain levels is observed, acetaminophen may be preferred (see 5.3 Specific Management after Evaluating Effects (1) When Analgesic Efficacy is Insufficient (Worsened or Unchanged)).

5 Strategies for Early Evaluation and Discontinuation of NSAIDs (Figure 1)

5.1 Time Required to Evaluate Treatment Response in NNP (Neuropathic/Nociplastic Pain)

In NNP, analgesic efficacy may emerge relatively early in some cases; however, generally, determining that a specific agent is clinically ineffective requires an observation period of at least 1 month. Moreover, even if a particular medication is judged to be ineffective, other agents may still be effective. Therefore, discontinuing analgesics for NNP after only 1 week based on presumed lack of efficacy should be avoided. Even if a specific analgesic generally considered effective is found to be clinically ineffective, this alone does not exclude the possibility of NNP.

5.2 Rationale for Evaluating NSAID Effectiveness Approximately 1 Week

To reduce NSAID exposure, it is important to evaluate NSAID efficacy as early as possible and to avoid unnecessary prolonged use.

The T_{max} (time to maximum plasma concentration) for most immediate-release NSAIDs is within 6 hours⁽¹¹⁾. In ibuprofen, the highest correlations were found between contemporaneous serum levels and pain intensity difference values⁽¹²⁾. There appears to be a relationship between NSAID concentration and effect⁽¹³⁾. A patient-level meta-analysis reported that a single dose of rofecoxib 50 mg demonstrated rapid analgesia onset (median 34 minutes) and prolonged analgesic duration (> 24 hours)⁽¹⁴⁾. In a network meta-analysis of pharmacological treatments for knee and hip osteoarthritis, most included studies evaluated NSAIDs, and treatment effects were generally similar between 1 and 12 weeks of follow-up⁽¹⁵⁾. Retrospective studies suggested that, in many cases, pain did not change even when NSAIDs were switched to acetaminophen 1–2 weeks after trauma or surgery⁽¹⁶⁾. A systematic review and meta-analysis showed that NSAIDs improve pain and function in knee osteoarthritis, with effects peaking at 2 weeks but decreasing over time; however, evaluations at 1 week were not included⁽¹⁷⁾. The incidence of minor GI and cardiovascular adverse events consistently rose, reaching statistical significance by week 4⁽¹⁷⁾.

These findings do not provide sufficient evidence to support evaluation of analgesic efficacy approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation. However, this evaluation may be delayed by up to 2 weeks. This time frame may serve as a pragmatic and operational reference point in clinical practice rather than an evidence-defined threshold.

5.3 Specific Management after Evaluating Effects

(1) When Analgesic Efficacy is Insufficient (Worsened or Unchanged)

If pain worsens or remains unchanged approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation, this suggests insufficient analgesic efficacy, and discontinuation of NSAIDs may be considered. However, this decision may be delayed by up to 2 weeks. Patients referred from other institutions may be managed using the same evaluation time frame. In this case, the cause of pain should be reevaluated. If the pain is judged to be predominantly NNP, prescribing analgesics effective for NNP should be considered. If the pain is judged to be predominantly NcP, switching to NSAIDs with greater analgesic efficacy

or opioids should be considered. Detailed explanations of diagnostic methods for reevaluation are beyond the scope of this review and are therefore not addressed.

Regardless of the duration since onset or pain severity, if switching from NSAIDs to acetaminophen results in similar pain levels, there is limited justification for continuing NSAIDs because of their higher risk of adverse events compared with acetaminophen. This may be explained by two possibilities: either both are equally effective or both are equally ineffective.

(2) When Pain Improves: Step-down Strategy

If pain improves approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation, it is difficult to determine whether this improvement is due to the actual analgesic efficacy of NSAIDs. In NcP, such as post-traumatic pain, postoperative pain, or pain associated with gout attacks, pain intensity often decreases naturally over time. Therefore, when pain improves, it is difficult to distinguish whether the improvement is attributable to the actual analgesic efficacy of NSAIDs, the natural course of the condition, or a placebo effect. However, in clinical practice, it is not always necessary to rigorously determine the cause of pain improvement. Based on the limited evidence from the retrospective study⁽¹⁶⁾, discontinuing NSAIDs or switching to acetaminophen may be considered when pain improves approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation. However, NSAIDs may be discontinued or switched to acetaminophen once adequate pain relief is achieved, without waiting for 1 week. However, this decision may be delayed by up to 2 weeks. It should be noted that reference⁽¹⁶⁾ used the period after surgery or trauma rather than the period after NSAID initiation. However, because NSAIDs are typically initiated shortly after injury, this period after injury can be considered to approximate the duration of NSAID exposure. If surgery is regarded as an artificial form of trauma, the same interpretation can be applied to the postoperative period. Therefore, taking these considerations and the inherently approximate nature of the time frame into account, it may be acceptable to evaluate pain approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation, and NSAIDs may be discontinued at that time. However, this decision may be delayed by up to 2 weeks.

Interestingly, pain may worsen even after discontinuing a drug considered ineffective in various clinical situations. As this phenomenon may not be identical to the conventional concept of the nocebo effect, we tentatively propose the term “inverse placebo effect.” Switching from NSAIDs to acetaminophen may represent a reasonable step-down strategy to reduce NSAID exposure while potentially mitigating the “inverse placebo effect.” Even after switching to acetaminophen, it is desirable to consider discontinuation approximately 1 week thereafter⁽¹⁶⁾. The proposed “inverse placebo effect” remains a hypothetical construct for conceptual discussion.

(3) Exceptions

In conditions such as severe acute gout attacks and inflammatory arthritis, where ongoing inflammation is a major contributor to pain, the proposed NSAID reduction

strategy may not be directly applicable and may require modification based on the clinical context.

(4) A Stepwise Approach to Modifying Prescribing Practices

To reduce overall NSAID exposure, it is important not only to optimize management in individual cases but also to reassess prescribing practice. NSAIDs are often continued for more than 2 weeks. In such situations, it may not be easy to immediately implement a strategy of evaluating efficacy at 1 week after NSAID initiation and switching to acetaminophen. Therefore, when immediate implementation is difficult, performing reevaluation at 2 weeks may be considered an interim strategy. Furthermore, if this approach does not result in significant issues in safety or pain management, the timing of evaluation followed by switching may be advanced to 1 week after NSAID initiation. This proposal is not intended to restrict flexible, patient-centered management, but rather to optimize prescribing practices.

6 Adverse events of Acetaminophen

Acetaminophen has traditionally been recommended as a first-line treatment for NcP because it is associated with a lower risk of adverse events than NSAIDs. However, its clinical positioning has been questioned due to concerns regarding its efficacy for low back pain and osteoarthritis⁽¹⁸⁾. Acetaminophen has traditionally been used at doses of up to 4 g/day^(19,20). However, a commentary citing several studies suggested that doses exceeding 2 g/day may increase the risk of GI adverse events⁽²¹⁾, and the safety of high-dose use remains controversial. In addition, acetaminophen has been associated with potential risks such as promoting antimicrobial resistance⁽²²⁾ and nephrolithiasis⁽²³⁾. Nevertheless, compared with NSAIDs, acetaminophen may generally have a more favorable safety profile. Therefore, switching from NSAIDs to acetaminophen may be considered a reasonable option from a safety perspective.

7 Use of COX-2-Selective NSAIDs

COX-2-selective NSAIDs have been reported to be associated with a lower risk of upper GI injury compared with conventional non-selective NSAIDs; however, no significant differences have been observed in the risk of lower GI injury⁽²⁴⁾, cardiovascular events (such as stroke and myocardial infarction)^{(25) (26) (27) (28)}, or renal injury⁽²⁹⁾. A study reported that COX-2-selective NSAIDs were associated with a higher risk of renal injury than other NSAIDs⁽³⁰⁾. A comprehensive analysis reported that COX-2-selective NSAIDs were associated with a lower incidence but greater severity of GI adverse events, primarily affecting the upper GI tract⁽³¹⁾. Therefore, continuing NSAIDs solely based on COX selectivity may not be appropriate, and reducing overall NSAID exposure itself may be important.

8 Topical Analgesics

One strategy to reduce the use of oral NSAIDs is to switch to topical NSAIDs. Topical NSAIDs are recommended because of their favorable safety profile^{(32) (33)}, and one study reported that they are safer than oral NSAIDs even with long-term use⁽³⁴⁾, whereas another study reported that the risks of adverse events, including acute myocardial infarction, GI events, and renal events, were similar between topical and oral NSAIDs during long-term use⁽³⁵⁾. Topical NSAIDs appear to be safer than oral NSAIDs, at least in the short term, and may be worth considering in clinical practice. However, as the long-term safety of topical NSAIDs has not been established⁽³⁵⁾, their routine or prolonged use without reevaluation is not desirable. Periodic evaluation of efficacy, for example, every 6 months, may be advisable.

9 Adjunctive Non-pharmacologic Strategies to Reduce NSAID Exposure

In cases of trauma, RICE (rest, ice, compression, and elevation) may be useful. These measures are safe, inexpensive, and can be performed by patients at home. In Japan, topical patches are often used for icing; however, because many topical patches contain NSAIDs, ice or cold packs are preferable.

Orthoses for chronic joint pain and trunk casts for thoracolumbar fractures may help reduce pain and NSAID exposure. An anterior-half body cast can be fabricated and applied on the day of the initial visit in the supine position, can be easily removed and reapplied, can be used without interfering with sleep, is low cost, can be reused for other patients, and does not require advanced technical skills⁽¹⁶⁾. Therefore, it may be a useful option, particularly in resource-limited settings or for pain management within the first week after injury.

10 Eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*

In addition to reducing NSAID exposure, other strategies are important for preventing NSAID-induced GI injury. One such strategy is the eradication of *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*). *H. pylori* infection has been reported to be associated with an increased risk of NSAID-related upper GI injury^{(36) (37)} and is a major risk factor for gastric cancer⁽³⁷⁾. Therefore, eradication should be considered for *H. pylori*-positive patients receiving long-term NSAID therapy. However, specific screening criteria for NSAID users remain a matter of ongoing debate.

11 Personal Clinical Experience

The NSAID exposure reduction strategies (excluding *Helicobacter pylori* eradication) proposed in this review were implemented in clinical practice, leading to a marked reduction in overall NSAID use. Although cases may have been missed if patients

sought care at other institutions, in the author's experience, no cases of severe NSAID-induced GI injury were observed.

12 Conclusion

The following clinical strategies are proposed to reduce the risk of NSAID-induced GI injury. However, the evidence supporting these proposals is currently limited.

1. NSAIDs may be avoided in patients with predominantly NNP.
2. Prioritize topical NSAIDs or acetaminophen for mild pain.
3. Analgesic efficacy may be evaluated approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation. However, this evaluation may be delayed by up to 2 weeks. Patients referred from other institutions may be managed using the same evaluation time frame.
4. If pain is reduced at the time of evaluation, NSAIDs may be discontinued or switched to acetaminophen to reduce NSAID exposure. However, NSAIDs may be discontinued or switched to acetaminophen once adequate pain relief is achieved, without waiting for 1 week.
5. If pain is not reduced at the time of evaluation, reevaluate the pain mechanism and consider modifying management: NNP-targeted agents may be considered if NNP predominates, or opioids or more potent NSAIDs if NcP predominates.

These strategies were implemented in clinical practice, leading to a marked reduction in overall NSAID use, with no cases of severe NSAID-induced GI injury observed in the author's experience.

As this review focuses on reducing unnecessary NSAID exposure, this approach may offer a practical strategy to prevent NSAID-induced GI injury. Furthermore, reducing NSAID exposure may help mitigate other NSAID-induced adverse events, such as renal impairment and cardiovascular events.

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NcP: nociceptive pain, NSAID: nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug, NNP: neuropathic or nociplastic pain

NSAIDs may be avoided in patients with predominantly NNP. Analgesic efficacy may be evaluated approximately 1 week after NSAID initiation. However, this evaluation may be delayed by up to 2 weeks. If pain is reduced at the time of evaluation, NSAIDs may be discontinued or switched to acetaminophen to reduce NSAID exposure. However, NSAIDs may be discontinued or switched to acetaminophen once adequate pain relief is achieved, without waiting for 1 week.